

**THE ROLE OF ENDOSCOPIC EXAMINATIONS IN EARLY
DIAGNOSIS DISEASES OF THE ESOPHAGUS, STOMACH, AND
DUODENUM**

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Relevance . In the modern world, despite the improvement in living conditions and living conditions of people, stomach diseases remain among the most common pathologies among the population. The simplest, most accessible, and informative method for diagnosing diseases of the gastrointestinal tract today is fibrogastroduodenoscopy. Since, it makes it possible not only to visualize the condition of the mucous membrane of the esophagus, stomach, and duodenum but also to take materials for histological and chemical analysis.

Objective: show the role of endoscopic methods in the early diagnosis of diseases of the digestive tract.

Materials and methods: The subjects of the study were 81 people aged 18 to 80 years who underwent fibroesophagogastroduodenoscopy (FEGDS) at the private clinic “Ibn Sino” in Fergana city from March 1 to September 1, 2023. A “Pentax” apparatus was used for FEGDS.

Criteria for inclusion of patients in the study: consent for FEGDS, the presence of ulcer-like syndrome in patients or non-ulcer gastric dyspepsia (abdominal pain syndrome and/or gastric dyspepsia syndrome).

Criteria for excluding patients from the study: refusal of FEGDS examination and absence of complaints of pain in the stomach and dyspeptic symptoms from the stomach and duodenum.

Results.

Statistical analysis of the fibrogastroduodenoscopy findings, shown in Table No. 1, showed that: 44.5% of the examined were male. In terms of age, the number of patients aged from 31 to 40 years old was more than in other groups. The percentage of patients by age group looks like this: aged from 18 to 30 years old - 29.6%, from 31 to 40 years old - 35.8%, from 41 to 50 years old - 13.6%, from 51 to 60 years old - 12.3%, from 61 years and above - 8.6%. The number of calls in the spring was 43 people - 53.1%, in the summer 38 people - 46.9%.

Table No. 1.

Analysis criteria	Total requests	Percentage
Gender:		
Male	36	44,5%
Female	45	55,5%
Seasonality:		
Spring	43	53,1%
Summer	38	46,9%
Age:		
from 18 to 30 years old	24	26,9%
from 31 to 40 years old	29	35,8%
from 41 to 50 years	11	13,6%
from 51 to 60 years old	10	12,3%
from 61 years and above	7	8,6%
Place of residence:		
rural population	47	58%
urban population	34	42%
Total requests:	81	

As is known, morbidity may be associated with a violation of the diet and regime [1, 2]. Thus, 70% of interviewed patients does not eat breakfast, eats “fast food” during the daytime in catering establishments, “on your feet” or in the workplace. Most people use semi-finished products for cooking and other products containing preservatives, food colorings and other substances that increase appetite. Nervous disorders, worries, stressful situations at work and at home, uncontrolled use of antibiotics often lead to disruption of stomach functions. Sometimes the cause of the disease is the insidious bacterium *Helicobacter pylori* [3]. Therefore, we believe that timely diagnosis is important.

Since early diagnosis of diseases of the digestive tract will make it possible to effectively treat them, prevent complications (bleeding, perforation, penetration, neoplasm, etc.), reduce the number of days and monetary costs of treatment. The fastest, most effective and reliable method for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal diseases is endoscopic examination.

The relevance of early diagnosis of acute and chronic gastritis is due to the fact that they are harbingers of not only gastric ulcers, but also precancerous changes (metaplasia and dysplasia of various types and severity). With the advent of new digital video endoscopic equipment using NBI-technology (Narrow Band Imaging) - spectral imaging in a narrow range of light waves - the identification of hearth of structural changes in the gastric mucosa has improved [4].

The prevalence and chronic flow of these diseases, accompanied by persistent loss of ability to work, cause their social significance. Untimely diagnosis and treatment of patients pose a threat to the lives of patients.

Conclusions: Carrying out FGDS in patients with complaints of stomach pain will make it possible to begin timely treatment of diseases of the esophagus, stomach and duodenum, as well as to detect precancerous changes in the mucous membrane in the early stages.

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